

Oxidation with Potassium Permanganate in Presence of Fluoride. Volumetric and Potentiometric Determination of Hydrazine

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Hydrazine is oxidized quantitatively directly or indirectly in acid solutions containing fluoride ions with KMnO_4 , in the presence of Cu^{2+} as catalyst to yield nitrogen and water by the uptake of 4-electrons. However, the oxidation in absence of this catalyst is incomplete. The different conditions favouring the quantitative determination of hydrazine by both volumetric and potentiometric methods are established. Amounts of hydrazine as low as 0.32 mg could be estimated. The titration curves obtained are characterized by two inflections, corresponding to the Mn^{3+} and the Mn^{2+} states respectively.

THE estimation of hydrazine is based on its tendency to become oxidized to nitrogen and water. Oxidizing agents usually used are iodate¹, bromate², ferric sulphate³ and ceric sulphate⁴. Kolthoff⁵ studied the oxidation of hydrazine with KMnO_4 in solutions containing 4 *N* HCl, but the results were unsatisfactory. Cay, Resenbery, and Bray⁶ showed that the different products formed during the oxidation of hydrazine by KMnO_4 are responsible for the variable results on account of their transformation to higher valency states. Issa and Issa⁷ determined hydrazine by its oxidation in alkaline solution with KMnO_4 . In the present investigation, the oxidation of N_2H_4 with MnO_4^- is studied in acid solution containing fluoride ions in order to establish the conditions favouring a quantitative determination of very trace amounts of this compound.

Experimental

A. Preparation of solutions :

0.1 *N* KMnO_4 was prepared by a method similar to that recommended by Stamm⁸ and standardised with AR sodium oxalate⁹. The hydrazine solution was obtained by dissolving the AR product in redistilled water. The reducing power of such solutions was determined by recommended procedure¹.

2% NaF, 1 *M* H_2SO_4 , 0.25*M* CuSO_4 solutions were prepared from the A.R. product.

B. The titration device used in the case of potentiometric titration : It is same as previously described¹⁰. The volume of the mixture titrated was always kept constant at 100 ml.

Results and Discussion

As seen from the preceding literature survey, the oxidation of hydrazine in acid solutions with MnO_4^- is not directly applied to the quantitative determination of hydrazine, whereas the reaction in alkaline medium can be utilized for this purpose⁷. The oxidation of

hydrazine can be considered to proceed according to the following mechanisms :

(a) Two electron mechanism

(b) Four electron mechanism

By the aid of the values of $E_0 \text{N}_2/\text{N}_2\text{H}_4 = 0.23$ volt and of $E_0 \text{MnO}_4^-/\text{Mn}^{3+} = 1.575$ volt, the calculated *K* and α values are 1×10^{12} and 1.6×10^{15} which show that the reaction (b) should proceed quantitatively.

Oxidation with MnO_4^- in acid solutions containing fluoride ions yields Mn^{3+} as a quantitative reduction product. The attainment of this state is favoured in the presence of a relatively high concentration of NaF (not less than 40 ml 2% per 100 of the reaction mixture). This condition was found to be a common factor with many reductants^{11, 12}; hence this point will not be discussed in the present work. However, other factors play an important role in the oxidation process.

I. Volumetric determination of hydrazine :

A—Oxidation of hydrazine with potassium permanganate : On titrating hydrazine solutions with MnO_4^- in presence of fluoride ions, the reaction occurring depends mainly on the acidity of the medium and the presence of Cu^{2+} as catalyst. Table 1, indicates that on performing the titrations in absence of Cu^{2+} , the oxidation of N_2H_4 in acid solutions with MnO_4^- proceeds more or less in accordance with the 2-electron mechanism. From the results shown in Table 2, the presence of Cu^{2+} ions does not only lead to improvement of the end point as in case of many reducing agents^{11, 12}, but also causes an enhancement of the

TABLE—1

TITRATION OF 5 ml. 0.02 M N_2H_4 WITH 0.0816 N $KMnO_4$ USING VARYING QUANTITIES OF 0.50 M H_2SO_4 IN PRESENCE OF 50 ml 2% NaF

Volume of 0.50 M H_2SO_4 ml.	Volume of $KMnO_4$ consumed ml	Theoretical end point on base of		Error %	
		2 elec.	4 elec.	2 elec.	4 elec.
1	2.45	2.48	4.96	-1.21	High
2	2.40	2.48	4.96	-3.22	High
4	2.30	2.48	4.96	-7.25	High
6	2.10	2.48	4.96	-15.32	High
10	2.00	2.48	4.96	-19.35	High

TABLE—2

TITRATION OF 5 ml. 0.02 M N_2H_4 WITH 0.0816 N $KMnO_4$ USING VARYING QUANTITIES OF 0.25 M $CuSO_4$ IN PRESENCE OF 50 ml 2% NaF AND 1 ml 0.50 H_2SO_4 .

Volume of 0.25 M $CuSO_4$ ml	Volume of $KMnO_4$ consumed ml	Theoretical end point on base of		Error %	
		2 elec.	4 elec.	2 elec.	4 elec.
1	4.65	2.48	4.96	High	-6.25
2	4.85	2.48	4.96	High	-2.21
3	4.90	2.48	4.96	High	-1.21
4	5.00	2.48	4.96	High	+0.80
5	5.00	2.48	4.96	High	+0.80

TABLE—3

VISUAL TITRATION OF 5 ml. 0.02 M N_2H_4 WITH 0.0816 N $KMnO_4$ USING VARYING QUANTITIES OF 0.50 M H_2SO_4 IN PRESENCE OF 5 ml 0.25 M $CuSO_4$ AND 50 ml 2% NaF

Volume of 0.50 M H_2SO_4 ml	Volume of $KMnO_4$ consumed ml	Theoretical end point on base of 4 elec. (a)	Error %	Max. Inflection mV/0.10 ml $KMnO_4$
1	5.0	4.96	+0.80	
3	4.98	4.96	+0.40	
5	4.98	4.96	+0.40	
10	4.95	4.96	-0.20	
20	4.45	4.96	-10.28	
40	3.85	4.96	-22.38	
(b)				
POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATION OF 5 ml 0.01375 M HYDRAZINE WITH 0.0412 N $KMnO_4$				
2	6.68	6.70	-0.29	155
5	6.70	6.70	—	200
7.5	6.60	6.70	-1.48	150
10	6.50	6.70	-2.10	150
15	5.82	6.70	-12.13	140
20	5.38	6.70	-12.70	140

4-electron mechanism. Consequently the end point is retarded due to the participation of the 4-electron step in the oxidation process as the Cu^{2+} ion concentration increases, till it coincides fairly well with the one corresponding to the oxidation of N_2H_4 to N_2 and water. This denotes a quantitative oxidation of N_2H_4 when the solution is $\sim 0.01 M$ with respect to Cu^{2+} .

Effect of acidity: The effect of acidity on the end point can be visualised from the data shown in Table 3(a). The most suitable acidity for attaining quantitative results is $0.005-0.05 M \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$. At higher acidities the end point is attained earlier and the error increases, which is due to the partial reduction of MnO_4^- to bivalent manganese or the participation of the 2-electron mechanism at higher acidities.

Effect of temperature: As can be seen from the data in Table 4 good results are obtained when the titrations were performed under the proper conditions of acidity and fluoride concentration at temperature ranging between 25° and 35° .

Effect of Hydrazine concentration: Table 5(a), shows that, very small amounts of hydrazine varying between 0.32 mg—390 mg can be determined quantitatively with very good accuracy. With larger amounts of hydrazine, the end points are attained earlier than those expected, a fact which is readily attributed to the production of N_2O .

TABLE -4

TITRATION OF 5 ml 0.02 M N_2H_4 WITH 0.0816 N KMnO_4 AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES IN PRESENCE OF 4 ml 0.50 M H_2SO_4 , 50 ml 2% NaF AND 5 ml 0.25 M CuSO_4 .

Temperature °C	Volume of KMnO_4 consumed ml	Theoretical end point on base of 4 elec.	Error %
25	4.96	4.98	+0.40
35	4.96	4.98	+0.40
50	4.96	4.93	-8.27

TABLE-5

TITRATION OF 0.02 M N_2H_4 WITH 0.0348 N KMnO_4 IN PRESENCE OF 4 ml 0.50 M H_2SO_4 , 50 ml 2% NaF AND 5 ml 0.25 M CuSO_4 .

Volume of 0.02M N_2H_4 ml	Amounts of N_2H_4 in mg	Volume of KMnO_4 consumed ml	Theoretical end point on base of 4 elec.	Error %	Max infection mV/0.1 ml KMnO_4
0.50	0.32	(a) 1.15	1.15	—	
1	0.64	2.30	2.30	—	
2	1.28	4.62	4.60	+0.43	
4	2.56	9.20	9.20	—	
6	3.84	13.75	13.80	-0.36	
8	5.12	17.60	18.40	-4.34	
10	6.40	21.85	23.0	-5.00	

(b)

POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATION OF 0.01425 M N_2H_4 WITH 0.0415 N KMnO_4

2	0.91	2.73	2.74	-0.36	170
5	2.28	6.83	6.85	-0.29	170
7.5	3.42	10.36	10.40	-0.38	160
10	5.56	12.25	13.30	-7.90	150

TITRATION OF 0.001375 M N_2H_4 WITH 0.0342 N KMnO_4

2	0.088	3.70	3.21	+15.26	25
5	0.22	9.10	8.03	+13.32	25

B. Reduction of potassium permanganate with hydrazine: When MnO_4^- is titrated with hydrazine in absence of Cu^{2+} , hydrazine yields a mixture of products corresponding to the 2 and 4-electron mechanisms as can be seen from the data cited in Table 6. However, when the reaction is performed in presence of $\sim 0.125 M$ $CuSO_4$, hydrazine is readily oxidized to N_2 (c.f. Table 7).

Effect of Acidity: As indicated from the data in Table 8(a), when MnO_4^- is titrated with hydrazine in presence of Cu^{2+} ion, the volume of N_2H_4 solution consumed in the titration increases and attains a constant value at acidities varying from 0.05 – 0.125 M

H_2SO_4 . This latter value corresponds to the quantitative oxidation of N_2H_4 to N_2 via the 4-electron mechanism.

Effect of temperature: Good results are obtained under the optimum conditions of acidity and fluoride concentration at $25^\circ - 35^\circ$ on the basis of oxidation of hydrazine to nitrogen and reduction of MnO_4^- to Mn^{3+} . Higher temperatures must be avoided, due to the partial reduction of MnO_4^- to MnO_2 (c.f. Table 9).

Effect of potassium permang.nate concentration: As can be seen from the data in Table 10(a), amounts of manganese varying from 0.24 mg up to 12 mg could be determined quantitatively.

TABLE—6

TITRATION OF 5 ml 0.0345 N $KMnO_4$ WITH 0.00925 M N_2H_4 USING VARYING QUANTITIES OF 0.50 M H_2SO_4 IN PRESENCE OF 50 ml 2% NaF.

Volume of 0.50 M H_2SO_4 ml	Volume of N_2H_4 consumed ml	Theoretical end point on base of		Error %	
		2 elec.	4 elec.	2 elec.	4 elec.
1	5.60	9.32	4.66	-40.0	+20.20
3	5.30	9.32	4.66	-43.10	+13.70
5	5.50	9.32	4.66	-41.00	+18.00
7	6.00	9.32	4.66	-35.60	+28.50
10	6.50	9.32	4.66	-30.30	+39.50

TABLE—7

TITRATION OF 5 ml 0.0345 N $KMnO_4$ WITH 0.00925 M N_2H_4 USING VARYING QUANTITIES OF 0.25 M $CuSO_4$ IN PRESENCE OF 10 ml 0.50 M H_2SO_4 AND 50 ml 2% NaF.

Volume of 0.25 M $CuSO_4$ ml	Volume of N_2H_4 consumed ml	Theoretical end point on base of 4 elec.	Error %
0	6.50	4.66	+39.50
1	5.40	4.66	+15.90
3	4.70	4.66	+0.86
5	4.65	4.66	-0.20

TABLE—8

TITRATION OF 5 ml 0.0345 N $KMnO_4$ WITH 0.00925 M N_2H_4 USING VARYING QUANTITIES OF 0.5 M H_2SO_4 IN PRESENCE OF 50 ml 2% NaF AND 5 ml 0.25 M $CuSO_4$.

Volume of 0.50 M H_2SO_4 ml	Volume of N_2H_4 consumed ml	Theoretical point on base of 4 elec.	Error %	Max. Inflection mV/0.1 ml N_2H_4
1	4.30	4.66	-7.70	
3	4.40	4.66	-5.60	
5	4.50	4.66	-3.43	
7	4.60	4.66	-1.41	
10	4.65	4.66	-0.21	
15	4.65	4.66	-0.21	
25	4.65	4.66	-0.21	
40	5.25	4.66	+12.66	
(b)				
POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATION OF 5 ml 0.0405 N $KMnO_4$ WITH 0.01425 M N_2H_4				
2	3.42	3.55	-3.70	185
5	3.48	3.55	-1.97	190
10	3.52	3.55	-0.84	180
15	3.52	3.55	-0.84	200
20	3.56	3.55	+0.28	175
25	3.72	3.55	+4.80	220
40	3.80	3.55	+7.42	200

TABLE—9

TITRATION OF 5 ml 0.0345 N KMnO_4 WITH 0.00925 M N_2H_4 AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES IN PRESENCE OF 10 ml 0.50 M H_2SO_4 , 50 ml 2% NaF AND 5 ml 0.25 M CuSO_4 .

Temperature °C	Volume of N_2H_4 consumed ml.	Theoretical end point on base of 4 elec.	Error %
25	4.65	4.66	+0.21
35	4.65	4.66	+0.21
50	4.40	4.66	-4.34

TABLE—10

TITRATION OF 0.0345 N KMnO_4 WITH 0.00925 M N_2H_4 IN PRESENCE OF 10 ml 0.50 M H_2SO_4 , 50 ml 2% NaF AND 5 ml 0.25 M CuSO_4 .

Volume of KMnO_4 ml	Volume of N_2H_4 consumed ml	Theoretical end point on base of 4 elec.	Error %	Max. Inflection mV/0.10 ml N_2H_4
		(a)		
0.50	0.47	0.47	—	
1.0	0.93	0.93	—	
3.0	2.80	2.79	+0.36	
5.0	4.65	4.66	-0.21	
10.0	9.35	9.30	+0.54	
15	14.00	13.95	+0.36	
20	18.75	18.60	+0.81	
25	28.00	27.90	+0.36	

POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATION OF 5 ml 0.0405 N KMnO_4 WITH 0.01425 M N_2H_4 .

2	1.42	1.42	—	250
5	3.52	3.55	-0.84	175
7.5	5.32	5.32	—	170
10	7.30	7.10	+2.84	120

TITRATION OF 5 ml 0.00342 N KMnO_4 WITH 0.001375 M N_2H_4 .

2	0.60	1.25	-52.0	210
5	2.08	3.12	-33.3	160
10	5.05	6.24	-19.7	120

II. Potentiometric determination of hydrazine :

The oxidation of hydrazine with MnO_4^- in acid solutions containing fluoride and Cu^{2+} ions are also studied potentiometrically both directly and indirectly as in the case of the volumetric method.

A. Oxidation of Hydrazine by potassium permanganate :

Effect of acidity : The results obtained on directly titrating hydrazine with KMnO_4 are shown in Table 3 (b) and represented graphically in Fig 1. The data indicate that the end points concordant with the theoretical one, corresponding to the oxidation of hydrazine to nitrogen are obtained when the acidity range is 0.005 – 0.025 M H_2SO_4 . The titration curves obtained at different sulphuric acid concentrations are more or less smooth with inflections at the end point amounting on the average to 150 – 200 mv/0.10ml. At lower acidities, however, the titration curves show another less defined inflection occurring prior to the second defined one. This inflection becomes more

Fig. 1 : Titration of 5 ml 0.01375 M N_2H_4 in 50ml 2% NaF and 5ml 0.25M CuSO_4 and different volumes of 0.50M H_2SO_4 with 0.0412N KMnO_4 . a) 2 ml H_2SO_4 , b) 5ml H_2SO_4 , c) 10 ml H_2SO_4 , d) 20 ml H_2SO_4 .

apparent at higher acidities contrary to the second which disappears under these conditions. Such behaviour can be explained on the fact that, due to the production of Mn^{2+} which is then oxidized to Mn^{3+} by MnO_4^- along the second step.

Effect of hydrazine concentration : The results of titrating different amounts of hydrazine under the proper conditions of acidity, fluoride and copper sulphate concentration at temperatures between $20^\circ - 30^\circ$, are given in Table 5 (b) and represented graphically in Fig. 2. It is clear from these data that amount from 0.90–3.5 mg can be determined quantitatively. The titration curves are characterized by two inflections, the second amounting to ~ 170 mv/0.1 ml $KMnO_4$, corresponds to the oxidation of hydrazine to N_2 and the reduction of MnO_4^- to Mn^{3+} . However, on using solutions containing less than 0.90 mg hydrazine the end points are retarded, and the titration curves are characterised by weaker inflections (amounting to ~ 25 mv/0.10 ml $KMnO_4$). This may however be attributed to the oxidation of hydrazine to higher oxidation states than N_2 in very dilute solutions.

Fig. 2 : Titration of different volumes of 0.0145 M N_2H_4 in 5ml 0.5 M H_2SO_4 , 50ml 2% NaF and 5ml 0.25 M $CuSO_4$ with 0.0405 N $KMnO_4$. a) 2ml N_2H_4 , b) 5ml N_2H_4 , c) 10ml N_2H_4 . Titration of 0.001375 M N_2H_4 with 0.00342N $KMnO_4$, d) 2ml N_2H_4 , e) 5ml N_2H_4 .

B. Reduction of potassium permanganate with hydrazine :

Effect of Acidity : The results given in Table 8(b) show the effect of different volumes of sulphuric acid on the reduction of MnO_4^- with hydrazine in presence of 5 ml 0.25 M $CuSO_4$ when the acidity is made 0.05–0.10 M H_2SO_4 . The end point coincides fairly well with the theoretical one. The titration curves in Fig. 3 are characterised by sharp inflections at the end point corresponding to Mn^{3+} stage amounting in the average to ~ 200 mv/0.10 ml hydrazine solution. This inflection is followed by another one which denotes the tendency of hydrazine to be partially oxidised by Mn^{3+} via the 2-electron mechanism as indicated from the position of the two end points as the acidity is increased.

Fig. 3 : Titration of 3ml 0.0405N $KMnO_4$ in 50 ml 2% NaF and 5ml 0.25M $CuSO_4$ and different volumes of 0.50M H_2SO_4 with 0.01425M N_2H_4 . a) 2ml H_2SO_4 , b) 5ml H_2SO_4 , c) 10ml H_2SO_4 , d) 15ml H_2SO_4 .

Effect of potassium permanganate - Amounts of manganese ranging from 1 mg up to 3.75 mg could be determined with good accuracy (Table 10 (b)). The inflection at the end point (Fig 4) are sharp and amounts to (250–175) mv/0.1 ml hydrazine solution. The titration curves show the same characters as mentioned previously. Also, on using very dilute permanganate solutions, the end points are attained much earlier than the calculated one.

Fig. 4 : Titration of different volumes of 0.0405N $KMnO_4$ in presence of 20 ml 0.50M H_2SO_4 , 50 ml 2% NaF, and 5ml 0.25M $CuSO_4$ with 0.01425M N_2H_4 . a) 2ml $KMnO_4$, b) 5ml $KMnO_4$, c) 7.50ml $KMnO_4$, d) 10ml $KMnO_4$.
Titration of 0.00342 N $KMnO_4$ with 0.001375 M N_2H_4 , e) 5ml $KMnO_4$, f) 10ml $KMnO_4$.

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